

GENDER DIFFERENTIAL IN MARITAL SATISFACTION AMONG MARRIED UNIVERSITY STAFF

¹AKANBI, Esther Geyiojo and ²AYODELE, Kolawole O. (PhD)

¹Registry Department, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

²Department of Education, Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

Correspondence: iwegbueg@funaab.edu.ng; Tel:+2348038633640

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20591676>

Abstract

One key indicator of a relationship's success is marital satisfaction, which assesses the extent to which individuals find their marriage rewarding or fulfilling in light of expected goals, and how well their rewards in the relationship outweigh the costs. A key indicator of marital success is marital satisfaction. Therefore, this study examined gender differences in marital satisfaction among married staff in a Nigerian higher-education setting. The study adopted a survey design. A stratified random sampling was used to select participants across various units and job types (academic and non-academic) at the Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta (FUNAAB). Data were collected using the 48-item Marital Satisfaction Scale (MSS). Analysis was done using descriptive statistics and an independent t-test. The results showed that the majority of the respondents were male (59.5%), though a fair percentage were female (40.5%), indicating substantial gender diversity. The findings also revealed moderate level of marital satisfaction ($M = 148.16$; 61.73%) while no statistically significant difference was found in marital satisfaction between male ($M = 148.6$) and female (Mean = 147.6) married staff in FUNAAB ($t = .837$, $df = 318.18$, $p > .05$). The study concluded that marital satisfaction, as experienced, is not based on being male or female, but rather in relatively similar ways across genders among university staff. Therefore, it was recommended that proactive marital counselling interventions should be available and applicable generally, and not necessarily gender-specific.

Keywords: Gender Differences, Marriage, Marital Satisfaction, University staff

Introduction

Globally, marriage remains a pivotal social institution expected to provide companionship, happiness, a strengthened bond, emotional support, fulfilment, and a platform for building a happy home, all of which are needed for the overall well-being of married individuals, families, and a healthy society. One key indicator of a relationship's success is marital satisfaction, which assesses the extent to which individuals find their marriage rewarding or fulfilling in light of expected goals, and how well their rewards in the relationship outweigh the costs. Building on existing studies, marital satisfaction is a state of mind influenced by how the rewards and costs of the marriage are perceived (Ayodele & Ogunsanwo, 2020; Unal & Akgun, 2022; Bunker & Kucheria, 2017). Asa and Nkan (2019) stated that in marital relationships, the higher the costs, the lower the level of marital satisfaction, while the lower the costs, the higher the level of marital satisfaction and vice versa. This, therefore, illuminates the application of the Social Exchange Theory (SET) as a foundational framework for understanding marital satisfaction.

Recent reports indicate that marital satisfaction has been declining globally. Regan et al. (2025), citing Proulx et al. (2017), reported that up to a third of married individuals experience low marital satisfaction. Similarly, reports from the Hague Institute for Innovation of Law (HiiL, 2018) revealed that marital issues and crises constitute a large share of family dispute cases presented in various courts across Nigeria. This is evident in Ogun State, where marital disputes are estimated at about fifteen thousand (15,000) per year (HiiL, 2021). These outcomes are known to have implications for individual well-being, family stability, productivity, relational health, and workplace functioning (Tavakol et al., 2017; Asekun & Alaba, 2019; Umeaku, 2025).

Functioning optimally in any organisation requires employees to be in the right state of mind and to have overall positive well-being (Efegoma et al., 2022). A healthy marriage is often regarded as a key indicator of overall health and well-being (Margelisch et al., 2015), playing a crucial role in reducing divorce rates and fostering robust, stable marriages, which are essential to a thriving society (Brkljačić et al., 2019). Similarly, Ayodele et al. (2021) affirm that individuals' mental and physical well-being improves when they are happy in their marriages. The absence of this could lead to impaired health and well-being, reduced commitment to work, low motivation, low productivity, poor discharge in academic, research, administrative, and societal engagement, lack of empathy, and strained relationships, thereby affecting the prompt and efficient delivery of the institution's mandate.

Against this backdrop, it becomes imperative to examine how these dynamics manifest among university staff as a specific occupational group in an academic environment. Akinmayowa and Kadiri (2016) posited that university staff may experience marital challenges differently due to unique occupational stressors. These could include heavy and demanding workloads, teaching responsibilities, tight deadlines, long working hours, administrative pressures, the drive to stay competitive in research, meeting academic publication targets needed for promotions, rigorous performance reviews, and fierce competition, among other factors (Bakare et al., 2025; Fatoye & Bolu-Steve, 2025; Okoye & Eze, 2021). When these work-related stressors are combined with an individual's marital crises, their impact could be amplified and could manifest in risky behaviours detrimental to both the employee and the institution (Akinmayowa & Kadiri, 2016). Its effects are not limited to the couple or the organization; it could also affect children's development and deteriorate family functioning (Tavakol et al., 2017).

Beyond the work-related stressors, gender has been widely used in academic literature across contexts to debate whether men and women differ significantly in their experience of marital satisfaction (Asa & Nkan, 2019; Jackson et al., 2014; Gürel & Çopur, 2020; Kiani et al., 2020; Praise et al., 2020; Amirnovin & Ghaffarian, 2018). However, the findings are mixed. For instance, Kiani et al. (2020) found that women are more prone to dissatisfaction, whereas men may avoid unwanted exchanges involved in marital conflict; women may not, thereby affecting satisfaction levels differently. Similarly, Dobrowolska et al. (2020) found that men reported greater marital satisfaction than women. Gürel and Çopur's (2020) study found that women reported more marital disagreement and a higher risk of dissolution than men. By contrast, studies such as those by Javanmard and Garegozlo (2013), Amirnovin and Ghaffarian (2018), and Praise et al. (2020) reported no significant difference in satisfaction between genders, highlighting that these findings may be context-sensitive. Despite these mixed findings, there

is limited empirical evidence focusing on gender differences in marital satisfaction among both academic and non-academic university staff.

Not finding a lasting solution to the lack of marital satisfaction across genders may gradually shift the marital relationship from a harmonious, support-oriented partnership to a source of stress. This could lead to more reports of couples' dissatisfaction, thereby increasing marital crises among university staff, their families, and society at large. It could also mean more children being raised in conflict-ridden homes, more deteriorated employees' well-being and low productivity, and undermined societal stability, as marital satisfaction remains a critical indicator of health and stability in marriages, families, and, by extension, the society.

Therefore, examining gender differences in marital satisfaction among this married staff in Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta (FUNAAB), where both male and female employees share similar professional roles and are often exposed to work-related pressures, is particularly important. Understanding this could help provide targeted insight into whether counselling interventions for marital issues should be gender-specific or universally applicable.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of marital satisfaction among employees at FUNAAB?
2. Will there be any significant difference between male and female married employees of FUNAAB on marital satisfaction?

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to examine gender differential in marital satisfaction among married university staff. This design enabled the systematic collection of data from a sample of the population in the University without manipulating variables. It also allowed the description of variables and the comparison between groups.

Population

The target population comprised all married staff employed at the Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta (FUNAAB), Ogun State, Nigeria. Information on the nominal roll obtained from the University's Personnel Records and Statistics Unit after due approval revealed that as at the time of the study, there were two thousand, and eighty-eight (2,088) married staff at FUNAAB, comprising 583 Academic Staff and 1,505 Non-Academic Staff as at the time of the study.

Sampling and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 336 married staff was calculated using Taro Yamane. A two-step stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure adequate representation of academic and non-academic staff. The population was first stratified into two primary strata by staff category, with the sample size distributed proportionally to the population sizes across the two strata, yielding a total of 94 academic staff and 242 non-academic staff. In the second step, each primary stratum was sub-stratified by colleges and units (for academic staff) and by units/centres/departments (for non-academic staff), and the allocated samples were distributed

proportionally to size within each sub-stratum of the academic and non-academic staff strata. Respondents within each sub-stratum were thereafter selected using simple random sampling

Instrumentation

A structured survey questionnaire was used as the research instrument for this study. It consists of the Sociodemographic Data Inventory (SDI) and an adapted Marital Satisfaction Scale (MSS) as developed by Roach, Frazier, and Bowden in 1981. The SDI provided data on the respondents' sociodemographic factors, such as age, gender, marital status, years in marriage, job type (academic or non-academic), while the MSS, containing 48 items, elicited information on the respondents' overall marital satisfaction level, using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 5 = Strongly Agree to 1 = Strongly Disagree. Higher total scores indicated higher marital satisfaction, and vice versa. The scale is reported to have high internal consistency, with $\alpha = .92$ (Fatima, 2021). Angusamy et al. (2017) also reported a satisfactory Cronbach's alpha coefficient of $\alpha = 0.93$. Cronbach's Alpha score from the pilot test conducted among 34 staff members at a similar tertiary institution was .84.

Method of Data Analysis

The obtained data were subjected to descriptive and inferential statistics. Percentages, frequencies, and mean scores were used to describe the sociodemographic characteristics of respondents and to answer research question one, examining the level of marital satisfaction among married staff in FUNAAB. The independent-samples t-test was used to test hypothesis 1 at the 0.05 significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.

RESULTS

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics showing level of marital satisfaction among married staff in FUNAAB

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Marital Satisfaction	328	121.00	182.00	148.159	11.225
Valid N (listwise)	328				

Table 2: Descriptive results on the level of marital satisfaction among married staff in FUNAAB

Category	Criteria	Frequency	%	Remark
161-240	Above Average	30	9.1	Respondents with an above-average level of marital satisfaction
81-160	Average	298	90.9	Respondents with a moderate level of marital satisfaction
1-80	Below Average	-	-	Respondents with a below-average level of marital satisfaction
Weighted Mean = 148.159; Std Dev. = 11.225				

Table 1 reveals the extent of marital satisfaction among married staff in FUNAAB. Marital satisfaction has a mean score of 148.159 (61.733%), which is, on the average, given that the

maximum score obtainable on this scale is 240. Table 2 presents the level of marital satisfaction among married staff in FUNAAB. Their level of marital satisfaction was categorized as above average (161-240), moderate/average (81-160), and below average (1-80). The majority, 298 (90.9%) of the respondents had an average level of marital satisfaction, and 30 (9.1%) had an above-average level of marital satisfaction. With a weighted mean of 148.159, the level of marital satisfaction among married staff at FUNAAB is average. It could then be deduced generally that the extent of marital satisfaction among married staff in FUNAAB is moderate.

Table 3: Independent Samples t-Test for Gender Difference in Marital Satisfaction

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	Df	t	Sig.
Male	195	148.6	12.17	.87137	318.18	.837	.403
Female	133	147.6	9.69	.84032			

Table 3 presents the results of the independent samples t-test conducted to examine whether there is a statistically significant difference in marital satisfaction between male and female participants. The results were not significant ($t = .837$, $df = 318.18$, $p > .05$). Male respondents (Mean = 148.6) reported slightly higher marital satisfaction than female respondents (Mean = 147.6), but the difference occurred by chance and is not statistically significant or meaningful. The null hypothesis that there is no statistically significant difference in marital satisfaction between male and female married staff is therefore accepted. This finding indicates that marital satisfaction may not differ significantly by gender among the married staff included in the study

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that the level of marital satisfaction among married staff at the Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, is generally moderate. This supports the study of Karney and Bradbury (2020), who explained that marital satisfaction typically reflects a mix of supportive and challenging experiences within relationships. The result is also similar to the findings of Tavakol et al. (2017), who affirm that marital relationships are often characterized by varying levels of satisfaction due to communication patterns, emotional reactions, and expectations within marriage. This suggests that couples may experience positive interactions, such as companionship and shared decision-making, while also encountering disagreements and emotional tension.

Theoretically, the Social Exchange Theory (SET), as used in this study, posits that individuals evaluate the costs and rewards of a marital relationship, and when costs exceed rewards, marital satisfaction may decline. The finding of this study is therefore consistent with the studies of Dabone et al. (2022); and Ogungbola and Akomolafe (2019), who posited that marital satisfaction is influenced by the extent to which spouses meet each other's expectations. When marital expectations are fulfilled, couples often report greater satisfaction; unmet expectations may lead to dissatisfaction.

Therefore, this finding suggests that although many staff members enjoy certain positive aspects of marriage, such as companionship and emotional support, indicating that marriages are not largely distressed, there remain areas within marital relationships that may need improvement to move satisfaction from moderate to high. Issues of marital tension and strain,

such as disagreements over activities, regrets about the marriage, and expectations within the marriage, might affect couples' level of satisfaction.

Regarding gender differences in the studied population, there was no statistically significant difference in marital satisfaction between male and female married staff at FUNAAB. This finding aligns with Javanmard and Garegozlo (2013), Praise et al. (2020), and Amirnovin and Ghaffarian (2018), all of whom reported no significant gender difference in marital satisfaction. These studies indicated that men and women often evaluate their marital relationships in similar ways when they share comparable social and occupational conditions. However, the finding contradicts the work of Jackson et al. (2014) and Kiani et al. (2020), who posited that women sometimes report lower marital satisfaction, possibly due to greater emotional involvement and more frequent exposure to marital disagreements than men.

The difference in the mean score indicating male respondents ($M = 148.6$) having slightly higher marital satisfaction than female respondents ($M = 147.6$), is not statistically significant or meaningful ($p > .05$). This corroborates Adzovie (2020) study on marital satisfaction among married Christians in a developing country, who reported that although females reported lower satisfaction than males, the difference was not statistically significant.

According to the present study, male and female staff in FUNAAB appear to experience similar marital conditions. The observed similarity suggests that respondents' marital experiences may be shaped more by shared marital circumstances, which may result from factors inherent in the married staff that revolve around their communication, emotional reactions, shared interests and values, expectations, and perceived challenges within their marriages, than by gender differences. Professionals providing interventions should therefore target both male and female staff equally, rather than assuming that marital challenges are limited to a particular gender group and limiting interventions to only one group.

Conclusion

Findings from this study showed that participants' marital satisfaction in this study area was moderate, confirming growing concerns about marital issues in Ogun State and Nigeria at large, and the need for interventions to address distressing areas in marital relationships. Having more moderate levels of marital satisfaction than high levels highlights the importance of marital education programmes, relationship counselling services, and family support initiatives that may help married staff strengthen their relationships, improve marital wellbeing, and prevent further decline in the marital satisfaction levels of couples within families and the wider society. Also, marital satisfaction among married staff at the institution appears to be experienced in relatively similar ways by male and female employees. Therefore, proactive marital counselling interventions should be available, and professionals providing interventions should target both male and female staff equally while addressing marital challenges, rather than focusing and limiting interventions to a particular gender group.

Ethics statement

This study was approved by the Babcock University Health Research Ethics Committee (BUHREC), and it strictly adhered to all ethical standards established by BUHREC. Necessary institutional approvals were obtained.

Informed Consent

Participants provided their informed consent to participate in this study.

References

- Adzovie, R. H. (2020). Attaining Satisfaction in Marriage: A study of marital satisfaction levels of married christians in a developing country. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 12, 160–172. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v12i1.1682>
- Akinmayowa, J. T., & Kadiri, P. (2016). Stress among academic staff in a Nigerian university. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Stress-Among-Academic-Staff-in-a-Nigerian-Akinmayowa-Kadiri/d7e7ae229a805e733280ffc3f5ea7b31e936923>
- Amirnovin, E., & Ghaffarian, A. (2018). Assessment of marital satisfaction and happiness in men and women who are married at early age and old age. *RAIS Conference Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3303479>
- Asa, U. A., & Nkan, V. V. (2019). Gender difference in marital satisfaction of couples in rural farming households of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Psychological Research*, 6(2). <https://www.idpublications.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Full-Paper-gender-difference-in-marital-satisfaction-of-couples-in-rural-farming-households.pdf>
- Asekun, W., & Alaba, M. O. (2019). Psychosocial correlates of marital satisfaction among selected couples in Lagos Metropolis. *Nigerian Journal of Social Psychology*, 2(3).
- Ayodele, K. O., Obianue, O. A., Ossai-Opute, S. C., & Iro-Idoro, C. B. (2021). Communication, conflict resolution skills, and stress as correlates of marital health among couples in a selected Pentecostal church in Ogun State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Psychiatric Rehabilitation*, 24, 209–217. <https://doi.org/10.69980/ajpr.v24i1-2.642>
- Ayodele, K. O., & Ogunsanwo, S. T. (2020). An empirical assessment on domestic violence among married market women in Ayetoro Epe, Lagos State. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Review*, 10(3). <https://ijsshr.com/journal/index.php/IJSSHR/article/view/639/0>
- Bakare, O. Q., Coker, A. O., Saibu, M., & Durojaiye, T. O. (2025). Work-Related Stress among Academic Staff of a Higher Institution in South-west, Nigeria: A Cross-sectional Study. *West African Journal of Medicine*, 42(2), 90–96. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/40618379/>
- Brkljačić, T., Glavak Tkalić, R., Lučić, L., Sučić, I., & KaliternaLipovčan, L. (2019). A Brief Scale to Measure Marital/Relationship Satisfaction by Domains: Metrics, Correlates, Gender and Marriage/ Relationship Status Differences. *Drustvena Istrazivanja*, 28(4), 647–668. <https://doi.org/10.5559/di.28.4.05>
- Bunker, N., & Kucheria, V. N. (2017). Quality of Life & Marital Satisfaction in relation to love matched and arranged marriage couples. *Indian Association of Health, Research and Welfare*, 5(1), 1–6. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343920801_Quality_of_Life_Marital_Satisf

action in relation to love matched and arranged marriage couples

- Dabone, K. T., Essuman, J. K., & Nyarko-Sampson, E. (2022). An Appraisal of The Marital Satisfaction Inventory: A Psychometric Process. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 06(06), 657–664. <https://doi.org/10.47772/ijriss.2022.6618>
- Dobrowolska, M., Groyecka-Bernard, A., Sorokowski, P., Randall, A. K., Hilpert, P., Ahmadi, K., Alghraibeh, A. M., Aryeetey, R., Bertoni, A., Bettache, K., Błażejewska, M., Bodenmann, G., Bortolini, T. S., Bosc, C., Butovskaya, M., Castro, F. N., Cetinkaya, H., Cunha, D., David, D., & David, O. A. (2020). Global Perspective on Marital Satisfaction. *Sustainability*, 12(21), 8817. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12218817>
- Efegoma, Y. C., Ofili, A. N., & Isah, E. C. (2022). Job Satisfaction and Psychological Health of Staff in a Nigerian University. *Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*, 34(2), 63–76. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jcmphc.v34i2.5>
- Fatoye, M. G., & Bolu-Steve, F. N. (2025). Prevalence of Work Stress on Marital Stability of Married Lecturers in University of Ilorin. *Citeus*, 5(3). <https://doi.org/10.17977/um059v5i32025p314-323>
- Gürel, B., & Çopur, Z. (2020). Gender differences in determinants of family life, marital quality and marital happiness. *Uluslararası Avrasya Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 11(40), 358–379. <https://research.hacettepe.edu.tr/en/publications/gender-differences-in-determinants-of-family-life-marital-quality/>
- HiiL. (2021). Deep Dive Ogun Report - Summary - Justice Dashboard. In *Justice Dashboard*. The Hague Institute for Innovation of Law. <https://dashboard.hiil.org/publications/deep-dive-ogun-state-final-report/>
- Jackson, J. B., Miller, R. B., Oka, M., & Henry, R. G. (2014). Gender differences in marital satisfaction: A Meta-analysis. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 76(1), 105–129. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12077>
- Javanmard, G. H., & Garegozlo, R. M. (2013). The Study of Relationship Between Marital Satisfaction and Personality Characteristics In Iranian Families. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 84, 396–399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.06.573>
- Karney, B. R., & Bradbury, T. N. (2020). Research on Marital Satisfaction and Stability in the 2010s: Challenging Conventional Wisdom. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 82(1), 100–116. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12635>
- Kiani, S., Yaqoob, N., Javed, S., & Siddique, S. K. (2020). Relationship between personality factors and marital satisfaction among working married doctors: Moderating role of gender. *Rawal Medical Journal*, 45(1), 144–144. <https://www.rmj.org.pk/?mno=51258>
- Margelisch, K., Schneewind, K. A., Violette, J., & Perrig-Chiello, P. (2015). Marital stability, satisfaction and well-being in old age: variability and continuity in long-term continuously married older persons. *Aging & Mental Health*, 21(4), 389–398. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2015.1102197>
- Ogungbola, O. O., & Akomolafe, A. A. (2019). Marital Satisfaction: An assessment of its fundamental factors in Nigerian. *Marsland Researchers*, 11(3).

<https://doi.org/10.7537/MARSRSJ110319.05>

- Okoye, E. I., & Eze, U. M. (2021). Moderating role of social support in the relationship between psychological wellbeing and occupational stress among non-academic staff in Nigerian Universities. *Journal of Occupational Stress*, 33(4), 421–437.
- Praise, F., Ocheho, T., Alao, B. E., Nnenne, B., Yunus-Ali, A., & Nwosu, O. E. (2020). Influence of personality traits and communication styles on marital satisfaction of couples in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Prestige Journal of Education*, 3(2), 23–35. https://www.openaccessglobal.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/personality_traits_and_marital_satisfaction.pdf
- Regan, A., Walsh, L. C., Horton, C., Rodriguez, A., & Kaufman, V. A. (2025). Contextualizing marital dissatisfaction: examining profiles of discordant spouses across life domains. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1458129>
- Roach, A. J., Frazier, L. P., & Bowden, S. R. (1981). The Marital Satisfaction Scale: Development of a Measure for Intervention Research. *Journal of Marriage and the Family*, 43(3), 537. <https://doi.org/10.2307/351755>
- Tavakol, Z., Nasrabadi, A. N., Moghadam, Z. B., Salehiniya, H., & Rezaei, E. (2017). A Review of the factors associated with marital satisfaction. *Galen Medical Journal*, 6(3), 197–207. <https://doi.org/10.31661/gmj.v6i3.641>
- The Hague Institute for Innovation of Law (HiiL). (2018). Justice Needs and Satisfaction in Nigeria: Legal problems in daily life. In *HiiL Justice Dashboard*. <https://www.hiil.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/HiiL-Nigeria-JNS-report-web.pdf>
- Umeaku, N. N. (2025). Exploring the personality trait for marital satisfaction: a conscientious-marital-satisfaction model. *Interdisciplinary Journal of African & Asian Studies (IJAAS)*, 11(2). <https://nigerianjournalsonline.org/index.php/IJAAS/article/view/262>
- Ünal, Ö., & Akgün, S. (2022). Relationship of conflict resolution styles in marriage with marital adjustment and satisfaction. *Psikiyatride Guncel Yaklasimlar - Current Approaches in Psychiatry*, 14(3), 322–330. <https://doi.org/10.18863/pgy.1016806>